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Abbreviations

BCS	Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer
CASSCF	Complete Active Space Self-Consistent Field
CC	Coupled Cluster
CCSD	Coupled Cluster Singles and Doubles
CCSDT	Coupled Cluster Singles, Doubles, and Triples
CCSD(T)	Coupled Cluster Singles, Doubles, and perturbative Triples
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CoE	Center of Excellence
CSF	Configuration State Function
DCSD	Distinguishable Cluster Singles and Doubles
DFPT	Density Functional Perturbation Theory
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DMC	Diffusion Monte Carlo
DMRG	Density Matrix Renormalization Group
ECP	Effective Core Potential
EOS	Equation of State
FCIQMC	Full Configuration Interaction Quantum Monte Carlo
GVB-PP	Generalized Valence Bond Perfect-Pairing
H	Hydrogen
HPC	High Performance Computing
LLT	Liquid-Liquid Transition
LRDMC	Lattice Regularized Diffusion Monte Carlo
MD	Molecular Dynamics
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Machine Learning Potential
MPG	Max Planck Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften
MPI	Message Passing Interface
NECI	<i>N</i> -Electron Configuration Interaction
NQE	Nuclear Quantum Effects
OQML	Operator Quantum Machine Learning
PES	Potential Energy Surface

PIMD	Path Integral Molecular Dynamics
PT2	second-order perturbation theory
QE	Quantum Espresso
QMC	Quantum Monte Carlo
RDM	Reduced Density Matrix
SAPT	Symmetry-Adapted Perturbation Theory
SAPT(MC)	Multiconfigurational Symmetry-Adapted Perturbation Theory
SAV	Slovak Academy of Sciences
SD	Single Determinant
SSCHA	Stochastic Self Consistent Harmonic Approximation
TCHInt	TransCorrelated Hamiltonian Integral evaluator
TREX	Targeting Real chemical accuracy at the EXascale
TREXIO	TREX Input/Output
TC	Transcorrelated
TC-FCIQMC	Transcorrelated Full Configuration-Interaction Quantum Monte Carlo
TUL	Politechnika Łódzka
VMC	Variational Monte Carlo
xTC	excluding-explicit-triple-contributios transcorrelation
3D	Three-Dimensional

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1 Introduction

The Targeting Real chemical accuracy at the EXascale (TREX) Center of Excellence (CoE) is in the field of high-accuracy quantum chemical and materials simulations with a special focus on QMC approaches to the solution of the quantum many-body problem at the heart of atomistic physics, chemistry, and materials science. Importantly, due to their inherent parallelizability and high computational cost, QMC approaches, and thus TREX, are uniquely positioned to fully exploit the massive parallelism of the upcoming exascale supercomputer architectures. Work in TREX focuses on the development and promotion of an open-source, high-performance software platform of interoperable flagship codes and exascale-ready libraries in its area of applications.

Scope

This Final Activity Report D5.3 reports on the following goals achieved during the TREX activity:

- Test and demonstrate the use of TREX codes and workflows on (pre)exascale machines.
- Demonstrate that the combination of TREX software with (pre)exascale architectures leads to breakthrough QMC applications.

Report summary

We provide here a list of the main achievements done in WP5, that will be described in detail in the forthcoming Section.

- Large-scale calculations are now possible at unprecedented system size, yielding access to accurate extrapolations to the thermodynamic limit in extended systems by means of Variational Monte Carlo (VMC), Diffusion Monte Carlo (DMC) and Lattice Regularized Diffusion Monte Carlo (LRDMC) calculations;
- An optimized workflow, suitable for (pre)exascale machines, to generate MLP based on QMC data has been successfully developed;
- A combination of QMC, MLP and PIMD allowed us to make relevant and original predictions on Hydrogen (H)-based high- T_c superconductivity;
- Magnetism with exponentially large spin configurations is now doable thanks to the spin-adapted approach based on the unitary group implemented within FCIQMC;
- An Hamiltonian transcorrelated approach has been developed to efficiently include charge and spin correlations in the transcorrelated framework;
- Density matrix approaches have been optimized to tackle challenging systems such as the molecular interactions between molecules in out-of-equilibrium geometries and in electronically excited complexes;
- The accrued inter-operability between codes has been further extended to comprise a larger number of codes in the TREX family, including TurboRVB, NECI and GammCor.

2 T5.1 Two-dimensional materials

Introduction

We study two most common ways of tuning electronic properties of 2D materials, straintronics and layer engineering.

One of the most distinguishing properties of 2D materials is their ability to continuously tune their properties in response to applied strain, allowing strain well in excess of 10%. Straintronics developed as an emerging field enabling novel tunable functionalities, such as band gap or effective mass tuning. Study of straintronic properties is experimentally biased by presence of substrates and in the simulations by the achievable accuracy of the mainstream DFT and GW methods. Here, using the ultra-accurate many-body fixed-node QMC methods, we performed benchmark straintronic study of monolayer phosphorene [1] and MoS₂ [2]. 2D MoS₂ is commonly regarded as the quintessential straintronic material.

The other tuning option considered here is layer engineering. For instance, the band gap can be modulated from ≈ 2 eV in a monolayer phosphorene, to intermediate values in few-layer phosphorene, to 0.3 eV in 3D black phosphorus. Here we show some results of our fixed-node QMC study of bilayer phosphorene, and MoS₂ [10].

Methods & codes

Figure 1: Left panel: Structure and basic structural parameters $\{a, b, x, y\}$ of monolayer phosphorene, and Right panel: of monolayer MoS₂, $\{a, x\}$. For more details, see Refs. [1, 2].

The electronic quasiparticle band gap, Δ_f , in monolayer phosphorene and MoS₂, for structures, see Fig. 1, is calculated as singlet-singlet vertical excitation energy,

$$\Delta_f \approx E_v^{ss} = E_1^s - E_0^s \quad , \quad (1)$$

with E_0/E_1 being the ground-/first excited-states. We use periodic boundary conditions where E_0/E_1 were computed by the diffusion Monte Carlo (DMC) method in fixed-node approximation using single-determinant variational Monte Carlo (VMC) trial wave functions with the nodal hypersurfaces determined by DFT orbitals using the generalized gradient approximation DFT-PBE, at the Γ -point of the Brillouin zone, with short-range correlations described by the Jastrow factor.

Finite-size scaling was used for all excitations considered [1, 2]. As shown in Fig. 2, the “neutral gap” defined by Eq. (1) under present conditions corresponds to fundamental gap. For additional arguments, see Ref. [11]. Fig. 2 also depicts Δ_f in various alternative treatments (DFT, GW) and in

Figure 2: Left panel: scaling of the $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$ excitation in phosphorene. The red point corresponds to the estimated optical gap. Right panel: Comparison of Δ_f in monolayer phosphorene in various treatments, including the QMC in the present approximations [3] with experiment performed on a free-standing sample [4].

the present QMC modeling with the experimental result for a free-standing sample. The superiority of the QMC modeling is evident as it gives a result in chemical accuracy with the experimental value.

In phosphorene the strain was applied in both armchair and zigzag direction by adjusting the a and b lattice parameters, see Fig. 1. Determination of strained properties was treated as a full optimization problem in the space of four structural variables: lattice parameters a , b and two internal parameters x , y , see Fig. 1. The data for E_0 were fitted by 4D paraboloid functions used to find the lowest point on the x , y subspace, leaving us to further minimize only bivariate functions, $E_0 = f(a, b)$. The excited state E_1 is computed only at the minimum for the internal parameters x , y , see Fig. 3. In MoS_2 , only diagonal strain was considered and a scaled-down procedure to two-dimensional space was used. In MoS_2 the relativistic effects are known to be present in the electronic structure (A/B excitons, for instance). The spin-orbit coupling splittings are non-negligible but relatively small in MoS_2 . While they can be QMC-sampled, due to their magnitude and the associated CPU time cost, we have decided to add the spin-orbit splittings calculated at the DFT level perturbatively on-top of our non-relativistic QMC results. Our procedure allows to determine, in addition to the band gap at an arbitrary strain load, also the equilibrium structural parameters which are not known experimentally for 2D systems, see below.

Due to the necessity to perform finite-size scaling for each excitation considered and determine 25/7 QMC-calculated points to bracket each of the 4D/2D minimum on any strain potential energy surface (PES) in phosphorene/ MoS_2 , respectively, the numerical burden of these calculations was very large. For that reason, a very thorough code performance benchmarking was initially performed. Considering the TREX flagship codes, only TurboRVB qualifies. The first calculations/tests on the phosphorene system [1] were performed with TurboRVB on the (pre)exascale machine Marconi100 at CINECA. Given the substantial CPU resources consumed, at a later stage a benchmark with the alternative QMCPACK [12] was performed. QMCPACK was developed mainly for calculations on high-symmetry systems and therefore it uses tiling DFT primitive cells into QMC supercells which largely reduces the computational burden for high-symmetry systems, such as the 2D materials. Contrary, TurboRVB was mainly developed and used for systems with lower symmetries (for instance treatment of quantum protons with path integrals) and calculations are performed over the entire

Figure 3: The paraboloids (internal degrees of freedom at equilibrium) of the ground- (E_0^s) and excited-states (E_1^s) for the 4×4 approximant in phosphorene. The red/green lines indicate the offset of the ground- (green) and excited-state (red) paraboloids in the ζ_a/ζ_b plane.

supercell. In the case of phosphorene, a speedup factor of ≈ 25 in favor of QMCPACK was determined and led us to use QMCPACK for this research. When the symmetry is lowered, such as, for instance if defects are treated, the two codes are found to perform on par. Contrary, as a result of this benchmarking, the tiling approach will be introduced to TurboRVB to make the high-symmetry crystalline calculations more affordable with TurboRVB.

Demonstrations

From our simulations we have determined equilibrium structure properties for both monolayers which are not known experimentally [1, 2]. Furthermore, we have ascertained that phosphorene is an auxetic material with a negative out-of-plane Poisson's ratio [1].

In equilibrium, both monolayer systems have direct band gaps; phosphorene at the Γ point, MoS_2 at K. In addition, we have also calculated a range of other strain-induced transitions: $\Gamma \rightarrow X$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma'$ in phosphorene (transition at Γ but with strain-induced reordered LUMO/LUMO+1 states and resulting modification of transport parameters) and $\Gamma \rightarrow K$ and $K \rightarrow K/2$ in MoS_2 [1, 2]. Generally, the primary difference with DFT results (if one takes into account semilocal GGA PBE, and hybrid functionals such as HSE06 and B3LYP) are fairly strong vertical offsets of the QMC gaps to larger values, ranging from ≈ 1 eV to ≈ 2 eV, according to the functional used (see Fig. 2). We found that in phosphorene, the DFT functionals giving more realistic band gaps (B3LYP, for instance) fail badly in predicting the equilibrium geometries (B3LYP lattice parameters are $\approx 4\%$ off). From our data we have also determined the gauge factor (i.e. the change of band gap per percentage of applied strain), which in both systems is very large, of the order of ≈ 100 meV/%. The latter finding correlates with the measured values in monolayer MoS_2 of ≈ 50 - 200 meV/%.

In Fig. 4 we show the band gap phase diagram for the various excitations in phosphorene and MoS_2 [1, 2]. The boundaries are calculated as intersections of the potential energy surfaces for the different excitations. Comparing the regions of the phase space leaving the direct excitation unchanged, we found a $\approx 10\%$ tunability region in phosphorene and $\approx 1\%$ in MoS_2 . Thus, phosphorene exhibits a larger tunability than MoS_2 by about an order of magnitude. On the other hand, the MoS_2

1% tuning in the tensile region is in agreement with experimental findings and could only be achieved after adding the spin-orbit splitting correction to our QMC band gaps. The ability to tune into tensile region, especially pronounced in phosphorene, is important experimentally, as compressive strain mainly leads to sample wrinkling. The combination of a large gauge factor with a large tuning region into tensile strain leaving the nature of the excitation intact leads to a colossal strain tunability of the band gap in phosphorene. Comparison with the DFT results suggests that they are all qualitatively similar (band gap phase diagrams, gauge factors) except for the vertical offsets of the band gaps and the fact that different excitations scale differently with applied strain than in QMC. The latter fact leads to significant shifts of the boundaries of the excitations (for instance, halving the $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$ tuning area in phosphorene in the DFT description w.r.t. QMC), see Fig. 4. Hence, this property is a very sensitive indicator of the quality of the electronic structure treatment.

Figure 4: Left panel: Face diagram of the various excitations in the ζ_a/ζ_b plane in phosphorene. Blue lines correspond to fixed-node QMC results with the overlays outlining the $\pm 1\sigma$ error bar, hatched regions and the region outlined by black lines in the $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$ region correspond to PBE results. Adapted from Ref. [1]. Right panel: The boundaries between different excitations as a function of applied biaxial strain as calculated in MoS_2 . The dashed lines are the gaps with spin-orbit coupling corrections.

As an example of layer engineering, we have studied three vdW homo bilayers: phosphorene, MoS_2 , and hBN [10]. The three bilayer systems represent three very different realizations of a bilayer and we give here a brief account of the former two. Initially, we planned to study the electronic structure just at equilibrium interlayer distance (d_0). However, due to the unexpected behavior in MoS_2 , we have finally decided to study full interaction curves from compression all the way to large interlayer distances. We note in passing that vdW interaction is completely missing in the “regular” DFT theory.

The results are shown in Fig. 5 and represent work in progress. The behavior of the two systems is very different. Phosphorene bilayer has equal excitations on both layers and the E_0/E_1 energies perfectly follow the Lennard-Jones curves. The band gap at equilibrium is ≈ 1.7 eV, reduced from 2.53 eV in the monolayer as expected (no finite-size scaling found). We presume this simple behavior is a consequence of partial chemical inter-layer bonding (between lone pairs). Hence, the electronic structure is akin to that of a slab. The MoS_2 bilayer exhibits much more complicated behavior as the electronic structure spontaneously breaks the lattice symmetry and localizes the electron predominantly on one plane; the details depend crucially on the layer distance d and E_0/E_1 follow

Figure 5: QMC modeling of MoS₂ (upper panel) and phosphorene (lower panel) bilayers. Each panel contains a graph of energies (E_0 , E_1 , Δ_f in blue, red, and green curves, respectively) for the largest supercell considered and QMC-calculated charge densities of excited electron (green color) and hole (yellow color) at three different layer distances indicated in the graphs by circles. The blue and red curves are Lennard-Jones fits plotted against the x-axis rescaled by r^{-6} , resulting in parabolic functions. QMC points depart from the Lennard-Jones behavior in MoS₂ for the smallest interlayer distances analyzed here.

Figure 6: Schematics of the split of nature of excitation into intra- and inter- in a bilayer as a function of the interlayer spacing d .

the Lennard-Jones behavior only in compression (where the system is again akin to a slab) and at infinite d , where all excitation is on one layer only. At intermedium distances, there are significant deviations from the Lennard-Jones behavior and a very modest reduction of the band gap to ≈ 2.6 eV is found, hardly reduced from 2.69 eV in the monolayer. We are still investigating this effect. One possible explanation is provided in Fig. 6, which suggests that in addition to the essentially intra-layer excitations observed, there are also inter-layer excitations at those distances not captured by our

single-determinant modeling. An alternative explanation is that this is simply a finite-size effect (from a level crossing) which would disappear at larger sizes which, though, cannot be presently modeled. The motivation for this explanation comes from the observed motion of the “spurious” features away from the minimum and towards large distances as well as from the disappearance of those features altogether at very large system sizes in hBN.

3 T5.2 Electron correlation and nuclear quantum effects

Understanding the interplay between electron correlation and Nuclear Quantum Effects (NQE) is of paramount importance to describe systems such as H-rich materials, and water. The former class of materials has seen tremendous scientific interest due to the discovery of superconductivity under high pressure in H_3S [5] and LaH_{10} [13], whose critical temperature is the highest among the known superconductors, getting closer to the holy Grail of room-temperature superconductivity. Water is the “liquid of life”, and is affected by nuclear quantum effects as strong as the ones in H-based materials, due to the pivotal role played by the H bond in structuring the liquid and determining its peculiar properties. Given the key role of H to set the main characteristics of these compounds, we started from its condensed pristine form. As reported in the previous deliverable D5.1, using the QMC TurboRVB code deployed in a pre-exascale High Performance Computing (HPC) environment led to one of the most accurate determinations of the high-pressure phase diagram of H, where we focused on the atomization transition pressure towards a high-temperature superconducting phase. As described in the same deliverable D5.1, we also studied the Liquid-Liquid Transition (LLT) in the liquid H phase, by deriving a Machine Learning (ML) potential trained on QMC forces. In the D5.2 deliverable, we then reported our results for the protonated water cluster, with the astonishing maximum reached by the proton transfer rate in close proximity of room temperature, detected thanks to an accurate Potential Energy Surface (PES) and to the inclusion of NQE, successfully resolved by our VMC approach. We therefore refer the reader interested in these demonstrations to deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. Here, we report the most up-to-date progress in the TREX demonstrations concerning the study of H-rich materials at the real chemical accuracy in a QMC-HPC framework, namely the applications to the H_3S and LaH_{10} superconductors.

Demonstrations

Sulfur hydride

Sulfur hydride is one of the superconductors with the highest superconducting temperature ($T_c \simeq 203$ K) discovered so far [5]. The drawback of this high T_c is that it happens at very high pressures. The peak of the superconducting temperature has been measured at $\simeq 150$ GPa, and it has been associated with the ferroelectric transition involving the trigonal $R\bar{3}m$ phase (see Fig. 7b), stable at low pressures, and the higher-pressure paraelectric $Im\bar{3}m$ phase (see Fig. 7a), characterized by symmetric H-bonds [14], where the H atoms are located at the midpoint of the sulfur-sulfur (S-S) edges. In the $R\bar{3}m$ phase, instead, the H atoms are displaced and they form a local electric moment (or local non-zero polarization) at each H site.

Figure 7: H₃S crystal structures. **a** Crystal structure of the $Im\bar{3}m$ symmetric phase (smaller volume, higher-pressure phase). **b** The $R\bar{3}m$ asymmetric phase (larger volume, lower-pressure phase). d_{SS} is the lattice parameter of the bcc crystal.

However, the experimental detection of proton positions is challenging and it is hard to distinguish between the two phases above, from both an experimental and a theoretical viewpoint. Indeed, previous theoretical simulations locate the transition at lower pressures, raising questions on the origin of the discrepancies [15] with respect to the pressure P_c measured at the T_c maximum, and whether P_c should be related or not to the ferroelectric transition pressure P_{ferro} . To solve this puzzle, we go beyond previous state-of-the-art calculations by treating the electronic problem not only with the DFT-BLYP functional, but also at the QMC level, and we solve the corresponding nuclear Hamiltonian by PIMD. In order to do so, we developed a Three-Dimensional (3D) model for the H shuttling mode responsible of the transition, allowing for a collective and concerted motion of all the H atoms in the system, retaining only the spatial degrees of freedom of a single H site. This 3D model is proven to accurately describe the local proton distribution as a function of pressure, as benchmarked against fully *ab initio* PIMD simulations carried out at the DFT-BLYP level. Given the reduced number of degrees of freedom, we can then derive a similar model from extensive QMC calculations. To do so, for each volume and for every proton position, defined in a cylindrical grid around the S-S axis, we carried out QMC (VMC and LRDMC) calculations as a function of the system size, in order to extrapolate the corresponding QMC energy to the thermodynamic limit. These calculations have been run in a highthroughput mode on the Fugaku supercomputer.

By means of PIMD simulations based on our 3D-PES derived from QMC, we analyzed the proton distribution and the shuttling mode frequency as a function of volume/pressure. Phonons are computed through the quantum displacement-displacement operator recently developed in [16]. This approach yields the lowest vibrational excitations, namely the energy difference between the first excited and the ground state of the nuclear Hamiltonian, a quantity generally measured by vibrational spectroscopies.

Fig. 8 shows the phase diagram emerging from our calculations, which reveal that the ferroelectric transition takes place at much lower pressures ($P_{\text{ferro}} \simeq 80$ GPa) confirming the underestimation

Figure 8: Phase diagram of H_3S at 200 K determined by BLYP-driven path integral molecular dynamics with quantum protons. We report both the ferroelectric transition pressure P_{ferro} (black dots) and the region where the local polarization vanishes into a paraelectric $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ phase, bracketed by the peak of the variance of local proton displacements, i.e. the maximum of the local moment susceptibility (blue star), and the peak splitting of the local proton distribution into a bimodal distribution (purple pentagon). Between the ferro (orange region with $P < P_{\text{ferro}}$) and para (green region with $P > P_c$) phases, an $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ phase with disordered local moments is expected to take place (violet region). For comparison, the pressure of the experimental superconducting T_c maximum is shown by a teal diamond. This suggests that the maximum of T_c is reached when the local moments vanish, and not when the ferroelectric phase is formed, in contrast with previous belief. QMC confirms this outcome (see Fig. 9).

found in previous works. In the ferroelectric R3m phase, the protons are all displaced in a concerted way, forming a long-range order of displacements, or of local polarizations. However, we found that at higher pressures than P_{ferro} , above the ferroelectric phase and closer to the experimental superconducting T_c peak, the *local* proton density distribution along the S-S direction has still a bimodal shape, even without long-range ferroelectric order. Only above P_c this distribution becomes single-peaked. Moreover, in the same range of pressure around P_c , we detected a maximum in the variance of the quantum fluctuations of the *local* proton distribution, related to the local moment formation susceptibility. This has been computed by the normalized variance of the displacement-displacement correlator in imaginary time, which is the fingerprint of the occurrence of local polarization. In practice, between P_c and P_{ferro} the local electric moments are formed and arranged in a disordered way in the crystal. Only below P_{ferro} they will order with long-range correlations. On the other hand, above P_c , there is no local moment and the peak of the proton distribution is centered at the S-S midpoint.

This result proves that the peak of the superconducting temperature in sulfur hydride is not related to the occurrence of the ferroelectric long-range phase, but rather to the formation of a disordered

phase with $Im\bar{3}m$ symmetry characterized by disordered local moments (Fig. 9b). The T_c reaches its maximum when the local moments melt and each proton is free to move across the PES barrier in the middle of the S-S edge.

The necessity of a proper treatment of electronic correlations - granted by QMC - is reflected by the discrepancies in the Equation of State (EOS) determination between DFT-BLYP and QMC (see Fig. 9a). PIMD simulations driven by DFT-BLYP forces overestimate the QMC critical volumes. However, when converted into pressures, their overestimation is compensated by the EOS mismatch, resulting in similar critical pressures, as yielded by these two electronic structure methods, arising from error cancellations. Our outcome can be used to test the DFT-BLYP quality for this kind of systems. The work has just been published in npj Computational Materials[17].

Figure 9: Transition values from theory and experiment. **a** Equation of state for both DFT-BLYP (blue color) and QMC (red color) calculations of H₃S in the $Im\bar{3}m$ phase. The transition volumes and the corresponding pressures identified at different levels of theory using the density probe (peak splitting) are displayed by dashed lines. In this plot also the classical results and the SSCHA predictions are reported. **b** T_c as a function of pressure in H₃S and D₃S from Drozdov *et al.* in [5], Einaga *et al.* in [6] and from Minkov *et al.* in [7]. The shaded areas on each data set represent the pressure range when the transition occurs according to our PIMD results for the QMC PES, where the lower limit is based on the local quantum fluctuations analysis and the upper one on the density evolution.

Lanthanum hydride

H-rich materials with clathrate structures are an important class of superconducting materials. Superconductivity in these materials originates from large H-derived electron density of states at the Fermi level and from strong electron-phonon coupling (related to motion of H atoms in cages) [18]. Lanthanum hydride (LaH₁₀) is one such material, demonstrated to show superconductivity at $T_c = 250$ K and $P_c = 170$ GPa [19]. Phonon spectrum and electron-phonon coupling are important ingredients used to predict superconductivity, being of Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer (BCS) type. However, computing accurate phonons for H-clathrate materials is a true computational challenge, as it requires the calculation of an accurate PES at the electronic level and the inclusion of quantum anharmonicity in the nuclear sector. Previous studies have shown that failure to include NQE could lead to wrong

predictions of the stable crystal structure. Errea *et al.* [20] showed that all the other distorted phases of LaH_{10} in the pressure range of high- T_c collapse into a single highly-symmetric $Fm\bar{3}m$ phase when nuclear quantum fluctuations were included, using an approximate though quite accurate treatment of quantum nuclei called SSCHA. Hence, the importance of NQE calls into question previous studies that have not treated NQE for crystal structure prediction and phonon analysis [21]. In order to solve this problem, we go beyond the previous state-of-the-art calculations, by solving the nuclear Hamiltonian at the quantum level using the PIMD formalism. The electronic problem was treated at the DFT-PBE level and we also did some preliminary tests for using QMC to treat the electronic problem. Accurate phonon dispersions are extracted from the quantum thermal distribution function exactly sampled by PIMD [16]. The importance of NQE becomes immediately visible in the phonon dispersion plots (Fig. 10), comparing phonons computed using DFPT (harmonic level) and PIMD (quantum anharmonic level). PIMD phonons computed for the $Fm\bar{3}m$ phase are dynamically stable over the experimentally relevant pressure range, at variance with harmonic phonons.

Figure 10: Phonons computed at various levels of theories. Left panel: Harmonic phonons computed using DFPT. Right panel: Anharmonic phonons computed using PIMD. Large instabilities can be seen in the harmonic phonons in several regions of the Brillouin zone. PIMD phonons on the other hand are dynamically stable. The solver for the electronic part is DFT-PBE. First attempts to replace it by QMC via a MLP generation are under way.

Although accurate, ab initio PIMD simulations can be extremely costly. An interesting way to get around this limitation is to use ML to accelerate PIMD calculations. Recently, there has been a lot of interest in the development of MLP based on both kernels and neural-network architectures[22]. We utilised Operator Quantum Machine Learning (OQML)[23], a kernel based approach, and MACE [24], based on graph neural networks, to train an MLP for LaH_{10} . The MLP were trained on energies and

forces of configurations generated using PIMD, driven by DFT-PBE forces. The trained MLP were then used to drive simulations with larger supercells, to compute phonons efficiently and accurately. In Fig. 11a-b, we compare the radial distribution functions computed by ab initio Density Functional Theory (DFT) with those computed by MLP, and this at both classical Molecular Dynamics (MD) and PIMD. The resulting MLP are particularly accurate, with errors of 8 meV per atom and 0.16 eV/Å for energies and forces, respectively. The MLP are also quite accurate when used to compute phonons (Fig. 11c). Indeed, there is a nice agreement between harmonic phonons computed using ab initio DFPT and phonons computed using MACE potential.

Figure 11: (a) Comparison of radial distribution functions for classical MD driven by MACE and OQML models. (b) Comparison of radial distribution functions for PIMD driven by MACE and ab-initio DFT. (c) Comparison of phonons computed using ab initio DFPT and MACE (frozen phonon approximation). MACE phonons were computed at Γ and L points in the Brillouin zone

Any MLP could be only as accurate as the ground truth that it is trained on. Hence, we would like to apply the MLP generation scheme that we have developed to training sets generated by more accurate methods like QMC. However, since QMC methods are more expensive than mean-field methods, performing scaling benchmarks for QMC codes becomes essential, before running extensive QMC calculations in HPC architectures.

Fig. 12 shows the weak scaling benchmarks for VMC and LRDMC in TurboRVB, using the LaH₁₀ supercell containing 88 atoms, 168 electrons and 36 kpoints as targeted system. The calculations have been run on Leonardo Booster nodes (Cineca supercomputer/SCAI, Intel Xeon Platinum 8358 CPU, 2.60GHz, 32 cores per node). For the weak scaling, we set the number of walkers M to the minimum possible one (one walker per core) and increased the number of cores while proportionally increasing the number of walkers. The scaling is excellent and near-ideal for both VMC and LRDMC

Figure 12: The weak scaling benchmarks for TurboRVB. The benchmarks were measured using a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ LaH₁₀ supercell (88 atoms) with the dolg [8] pseudopotential (168 electrons in the simulation cell) on Leonardo Booster nodes (Cineca supercomputer/SCAI).

approaches.

This demonstration is still a part of ongoing research. For future plans, we would like to generate MLP with QMC forces and energies. We would also like to compute quantum anharmonic phonons using PIMD trajectories generated using a QMC-based MLP, to make a breakthrough not only in the phonon calculation strategy but also on the quality of the underlying potential.

Code used

In order to achieve the above results, extensive work has been carried out in TurboRVB to employ an accurate evaluation of forces by QMC, i.e., by using an appropriate basis set, a very accurate initialization of the Single Determinant (SD) wavefunction by the Gaussian DFT code provided with the TurboRVB distribution, carefully benchmarked against existing DFT packages (i.e., Quantum Espresso (QE)), and the use of the space-warp coordinate transformation that dramatically helps to reduce error bars, hence computational cost [25]. We have also obtained a significant improvement of performances by an extensive modularization of the TurboRVB code (within the WP3 package), for its use in Fugaku, the (pre)exascale supercomputer recently launched in Japan. Porting TurboRVB to GPU accelerated hardware (Marconi100) has also been very important, particularly for the wavefunction initialization of large supercells. In the realm of WP4-WP5 interactions, schemes to exploit QMC in combination with the MLP generation have been developed and their applications to challenging systems such as LaH₁₀ just started.

4 T5.3 Quantum magnetism and transcorrelation

Each electronic structure method has an inherent degree of accuracy which enables it to correctly characterize certain properties of certain electronic systems. The characterization of the quantum

magnetic properties of molecules often requires resolving relative energies in the meV range associated with highly multi-reference electronic states, posing a challenge to even the most accurate of quantum chemical methods. The development of new methods is the main path towards the ultimate goal of being able to compute properties requiring a highly accurate description of electronic correlation in real applications.

Direct spin-adaptation for multi-reference problems

The biological function of a number of important catalysts such as ferredoxin proteins and photosystem II, involving [FeS] and [MnO] clusters respectively, depends on the existence of multiple spin states with low energy, arising from the fact that these systems consist of high-spin centres effectively coupled anti-ferromagnetically to each other via exchange and super-exchange processes. These systems very often exist in structural configurations that lead to geometrical frustration, such as the tetrahedral cubane structure of the Fe(III) centres of [Fe(III)₄S₄] systems, adding to the complexity of the problem. The strongly open-shell nature of these molecules makes them extreme examples of *multi-reference* systems, whose many-body wavefunctions are not dominated by one or a few but by combinatorially large numbers of Slater determinants.

A *spin-adapted* basis of Configuration State Function (CSF) built out of appropriately spin-coupled Slater determinants is much better suited for the study of multi-reference systems than individual Slater determinants. The use of CSFs in many methods becomes cumbersome due to the combinatorial number of Slater determinants in a CSF as a function of the number of open-shell orbitals, effectively limiting its application to systems with up to 18 open-shell orbitals. The FCIQMC method has instead the ability to use *direct* spin-adaptation, without explicit expansion of CSFs in terms of Slater determinants, as already implemented in the *N*-Electron Configuration Interaction (NECI) code.

The main technical development in the present contribution is the evaluation of the 1- and 2-body Reduced Density Matrix (RDM) in FCIQMC within this spin-free formalism [26], enabling the calculation of properties that do not commute with the Hamiltonian, such as electronic gradient matrices, enabling CASSCF and orbital optimisation, and spin-spin correlation functions. The spin-free one- and two-body RDMs in terms of unitary group generators are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{ij} &= \langle \Psi | \hat{E}_{ij} | \Psi \rangle = \sum_{\mu\nu} c_{\mu}^* c_{\nu} \langle \mu | \hat{E}_{ij} | \nu \rangle , \\ \Gamma_{ij,kl} &= \langle \Psi | \hat{e}_{ij,kl} | \Psi \rangle = \sum_{\mu\nu} c_{\mu}^* c_{\nu} \langle \mu | \hat{e}_{ij,kl} | \nu \rangle , \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{E}_{ij}^{\dagger} = \hat{E}_{ji}$, i, j, k, l denote *spatial* orbitals, $|\mu\rangle$ and $|\nu\rangle$ are CSFs, and c_{μ} and c_{ν} their coefficients in the ground state wave function $|\Psi\rangle$.

The transcorrelated method

Describing electronic correlation is a difficult problem: while systematically improvable electronic structure methods exist that are formally capable of exactly describing electronic systems, this description is only accessible in the limit of infinite computational cost. Computationally affordable

methods tend to excel at describing either dynamic correlation (typically real-space methods such as QMC) or static correlation (typically orbital-space methods such as FCIQMC), but struggle to do both efficiently. The Transcorrelated (TC) method is a theoretical framework that enables the inclusion of explicit real-space dynamic correlation information into orbital-space approaches, which we focus on here.

The effect of a Jastrow correlation factor e^J on the Hamiltonian \hat{H} is absorbed into the TC Hamiltonian \hat{H}_{TC} using the similarity transformation

$$\hat{H}_{\text{TC}} = e^{-J} \hat{H} e^J. \quad (3)$$

\hat{H}_{TC} is non-Hermitian and has the commutator expansion

$$\hat{H}_{\text{TC}} = \hat{H} + [\hat{H}, J] + \frac{1}{2} [[\hat{H}, J], J], \quad (4)$$

which exactly truncates at second order provided the Jastrow factor is a scalar function of the electronic coordinates, $J = J(\mathbf{R})$. This enables transcorrelation to be applied as a relatively minor modification to existing implementations of orbital-based electronic structure methods, which must be able to handle the additional contributions arising from Eq. 4, namely (i) the non-Hermitian contributions to two-body matrix elements, and (ii) the Hermitian three-electron matrix elements. The FCIQMC method can be trivially extended to handle these in what we refer to as the TC-FCIQMC method, and Jastrow factors tailored to each system can be optimized within a VMC framework [27].

The xTC approximation [28] facilitates the implementation of transcorrelation by folding explicit three-body matrix elements L in a mean-field manner into the zero-, one-, and two-body matrix elements (E_{nuc} , h , and U , respectively) with respect to a reference wave function $|\Phi_0\rangle$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{E}_{\text{nuc}} &= E_{\text{nuc}} - \frac{1}{6} \sum_{PQRSTU} L_{PRT}^{QSU} \gamma_{QSU}^{PRT} \\ \tilde{h}_P^Q &= h_P^Q + \sum_{RSTU} \left(L_{PRT}^{QSU} - L_{PRT}^{SQU} - L_{PRT}^{USQ} \right) \left(\gamma_S^R \gamma_U^T - \gamma_U^R \gamma_S^T - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{SU}^{RT} \right) \\ \tilde{U}_{PR}^{QS} &= U_{PR}^{QS} - \sum_{TU} \left(L_{PRT}^{QSU} - L_{PRT}^{QUS} - L_{PRT}^{USQ} \right) \gamma_U^T \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\gamma_{Q\dots}^P = \langle \Phi_0 | a_{Q\dots}^P | \Phi_0 \rangle$ and $a_{Q\dots}^P$ is the normal-ordered product of creation and annihilation operators $a_p^\dagger a_q \dots$. This approximation allows the application of the TC method to a broad range of quantum chemistry methods, including the Coupled Cluster (CC) [29] and Density Matrix Renormalization Group (DMRG) [30] methods, which still need to be able to support non-Hermitian Hamiltonians but are no longer required to handle explicit three-body matrix elements.

Demonstrations

Direct spin-adaptation for multi-reference problems

We have computed ground and excited state energies of $[\text{Fe}_4\text{S}_4]$ clusters, consisting of at least 20 open-shell orbitals, using the the stochastic-CASSCF method. The corresponding electronic spectra

have been fitted to extended Heisenberg models to assess the accuracy with which such spin models reproduce true ab initio spectra. The exchange parameters obtained from such fits can be compared with experiment, and provide insight into the importance of the various active orbitals in the exchange and super-exchange processes that yield the anti-ferromagnetism [26].

The transcorrelated method

We use flexible Jastrow correlation factors containing dozens of parameters that must be optimized. The VMC method provides a natural environment to optimize trial wave functions, but the choice of target function to minimize must be investigated. Measures of the spread of the energy, such as the variance, are a traditional choice employed in early applications of VMC, while energy minimization, a more aggressive optimization strategy, is the current de facto standard in real-space QMC studies. In Ref. [27] we test both approaches on all-electron first-row atoms and molecules, and find that energy minimization yields Jastrow factors that tend to overcorrelate the electrons and produces relative energies that converge more slowly with basis-set size than variance-minimized Jastrow factors, as can be seen in Fig. 13. In Fig. 14 the convergence of FCIQMC and TC-FCIQMC atomization energies

Figure 13: TC-FCIQMC total energies of all-electron atoms (left) and atomization energies of all-electron dimers (right) as a function of inverse basis set size. Theoretical estimates of the corresponding nonrelativistic energies from the literature are shown as dashed lines with a shaded area at ± 1 kcal/mol. The cardinal number x of the cc-pV x Z basis used is shown as annotations in the top panel.

to the basis set limit is compared. In these results, the TC-FCIQMC results converge two cardinal

Figure 14: FCIQMC and TC-FCIQMC atomization energies of all-electron dimers as a function of inverse basis set size. Theoretical estimates of the nonrelativistic atomization energies from the literature are shown as dashed lines with a shaded area at ± 1 kcal/mol. The cardinal number x of the cc-pV x Z basis used is shown as annotations in the top panel.

numbers earlier than their FCIQMC counterparts, reaching chemical accuracy by the cc-pVTZ level. The computational cost of orbital-space methods, both in terms of memory and time, scales steeply with basis-set size, so the TC method can be regarded as a way of achieving high accuracy more affordably.

In Ref. [28] we assess the accuracy of the xTC approximation in the context of the CC family of methods by comparing atomization energies for a benchmark set of molecules using the xTC and F12 explicit correlation approximations. In these tests the xTC approximation outperforms the F12 approximation, and the results suggest that the use of the xTC approximation incurs a negligible error with respect to using the full TC approach for small molecules (see Fig. 15).

The development of the TC methodology will require further advances, in particular regarding Effective Core Potential (ECP) technology, to be able to handle complex magnetic systems which usually involve heavy-element atoms containing many electrons. However, as a preview of the ability of the methodology to obtain magnetic properties, in Ref. [31] we report preliminary calculations of the spin gap of the CH₂ molecule between the singlet 1A_1 ground state and the triplet 3B_1 excited state. This system is simple enough to be handled by the full TC method without requiring an ECP, but complex enough that a standard baseline method to handle multi-reference systems, CASSCF with second-order perturbation theory (PT2) corrections, struggles to converge. The FCIQMC method is best suited for single-reference systems, but nonetheless the TC-FCIQMC method using CASSCF orbitals effortlessly provides an improvement over CASSCF in the correct direction, while the PT2 correction worsens the spin gap, as can be seen in Fig. 16 The ability of TC-FCIQMC to handle this simple case well is a promising prospect for its application to more complicated magnetic systems.

Figure 15: Deviation from benchmark values of the atomization energies of the molecules in the HEAT benchmark set (points) and their distribution (curve) using the F12 (top) and xTC (bottom) explicit-correlation methods in the CCSD, DCSD, CCSD(T), and CCSDT frameworks at the aug-cc-pVTZ basis-set level. The “chemical accuracy” range around the benchmark values are shown as vertical lines.

Figure 16: Spin gap of the CH_2 molecule between the singlet 1A_1 ground state and the triplet 3B_1 excited state using the cc-pV x Z basis-set family. The TC-FCIQMC method using CASSCF(6,6) orbitals yields a spin gap within 1 mHa of the experimental value at the cc-pVTZ basis-set level.

Code used

We use the NECI code to perform FCIQMC calculations, which supports non-Hermitian Hamiltonians and three-body matrix elements. The ability to compute 1- and 2-body RDMs has been implemented

in NECI as part of the TREX project. The evaluation of the matrix elements of \hat{H}_{TC} is performed by the separate companion TransCorrelated Hamiltonian Integral evaluator (TCHInt) library, which has been developed as part of the TREX project.

For reference, a system with 100 molecular orbitals has over 20 billion potential three-body matrix elements to calculate. Using a smaller number of intermediate objects, each element can be computed independently from the others, making this a highly parallelizable task. TCHInt leverages this parallelism using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) framework, and is capable of using HPC resources with near-perfect efficiency. The subsequent NECI calculations are also able to run very efficiently on massively-parallel resources. The serial performance of TCHInt has greatly benefited from specialist code tuning, as offered in the TREX project.

TCHInt implements the xTC approximation as an option, which allows the computed matrix elements to be used by a broad range of codes with only minor modification. Integration of the TREX Input/Output (TRESIO) library into TCHInt guarantees the ability to serve codes in the TREX project other than NECI, and other codes in the broader software ecosystem.

5 T5.4 Van der Waals interactions

The ubiquitous Van der Waals interactions play a key role in layered materials which show great potential for rapid, dissipationless, and flexible next-generation electronic devices. Predicting both the structure and functionality of these compounds requires an accurate treatment of weak intermolecular forces—a task that exceeds the capabilities of simple empirical models. While most of the focus in material science so far has been on interactions in electronic ground-state systems, there has been a growing interest in excited-state complexes. The proper description of the dispersion energy in excited states becomes relevant for designing nanostructures with high phosphorescence quantum yields or optoelectronic materials. When modelling nanomaterials, it is also of crucial importance to take into account effects resulting from geometry distortions—covalent bonds stretching and twisting. The presence of either of these effects, electronic excitations or geometry distortions, poses an enormous challenge to the existing quantum computational approaches. The widely used coupled cluster response methods are practically limited to small- or medium-sized systems where electrons are weakly correlated. Density functional theory approximations are also inadequate, as these methods fail for molecules where short-range, long-range and strong electron correlation effects must be treated on equal footing.

In the TREX project, we focused on characterizing van der Waals systems based on partitioning the interaction energy into physically meaningful contributions. We covered two challenging situations: the variation of the interaction strength due to a perturbation driving the geometry of the system out-of-equilibrium, and the interaction energy modification due to an underlying electron excitation of a $\pi - \pi^*$ or $n - \pi^*$ character, the keystone of organic photochemistry. To address these problems, we had to develop and implement a novel set of computational tools. Their key component is the accurate and efficient prediction of the dispersion energy.

Dispersion interactions in electronic ground and excited states

A general formula for the dispersion energy of a molecular complex composed of two weakly interacting species A and B is well-defined in the perturbation theory as a second-order term in the interaction potential, and it reads [32]

$$E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)}(A_I B_J) = - \sum_{\mu \neq I, \nu \neq J} \frac{1}{\omega_{\mu}^{A_I} + \omega_{\nu}^{B_J}} \left(\int d\mathbf{r}_1 \int d\mathbf{r}_2 \frac{\rho_{\mu}^{A_I}(\mathbf{r}_1) \rho_{\nu}^{B_J}(\mathbf{r}_2)}{r_{12}} \right)^2, \quad (6)$$

where a transition density for an N_A -electron subsystem A corresponding to a $I \rightarrow \mu$ state transition, is defined as

$$\rho_{\mu}^{A_I}(\mathbf{r}) = N_A \sum_{\sigma} \int \Psi_I^A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots)^* \Psi_{\mu}^A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots) d\mathbf{x}_2 \dots d\mathbf{x}_{N_A} \quad (7)$$

(analogously for B). Until now, most implementations of this formula assumed that both monomers are in their ground states, $I = 0$ and $J = 0$, and their geometries are close to equilibrium. In due of the TREX project we have proposed and developed computational algorithms for evaluating $E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)}(A_I B_J)$ without restrictions on states I, J and with a favourable computational cost. The novel method is based on the assumption that monomers A and B are described with correlated (multireference) wavefunctions Ψ_I^A, Ψ_J^B , adequate for electronic states of interest. The quantities used in the evaluation of the dispersion energy expression are, however, compressed—they are one- and two-electron reduced density matrices (1- and 2-RDMs) of monomers

$$[\gamma_{\mu}^{X_I}] = \langle \Psi_I^X | \hat{\gamma} | \Psi_I^X \rangle \quad (8)$$

$$[\Gamma_{\mu}^{X_I}] = \langle \Psi_I^X | \hat{\Gamma} | \Psi_I^X \rangle \quad (9)$$

respectively, where $X = A, B$. It is worth noting that 1,2-RDMs are usually available from ab initio or QMC calculations run on classical or quantum computers. Another key component of the efficient computation of the dispersion energy was the reformulation of the expression given in Eq. (6) in a way that the summation-over-states (SOS) is avoided. It is known that SOS formulae are costly, as they require access to the time-dependent response properties, i.e. full electronic spectra (excitation energies, $\{\omega_{\mu}^X\}$, and transition density matrices $\{\rho_{\mu}^X(\mathbf{r})\}$) must be evaluated, that is the most computationally demanding step. The proposed algorithm is based on the formula equivalent to Eq. (6) reading

$$E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)} = -\frac{8}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} d\omega \text{Tr} \left[\mathbf{D}^{\text{T}} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^A(\omega) \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^B(\omega)^{\text{T}} \mathbf{D} \right], \quad (10)$$

which exploits the Cholesky decomposition of electron repulsion integrals, $g_{pqrs} = \sum_{L=1}^{N_{\text{Chol}}} D_{pq,L} D_{rs,L}$, and a recursive formula for frequency-dependent density response functions of the monomers $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}^X(\omega)$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\omega)^{(k)} = -k \bar{\mathbf{A}}^{(1)} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\omega)^{(k-1)} - k(k-1) \bar{\mathbf{A}}^{(2)} \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\omega)^{(k-2)}. \quad (11)$$

(see Ref. [33] for full details). Within the novel algorithm, the dispersion energy is computed for nondegenerate ground- or excited-state complexes with arbitrary spin, also for strongly correlated systems, at the cost scaling only with the 5th power of the system size. Remarkably, it is the same scaling as that offered by methods applicable to only ground state weakly correlated systems.

Multiconfigurational symmetry-adapted perturbation theory (SAPT(MC))

One of the methods suitable for studying molecular interactions in electronically-excited-state systems or systems in out-of-equilibrium geometries is the multiconfigurational symmetry-adapted perturbation theory Multiconfigurational Symmetry-Adapted Perturbation Theory (SAPT(MC)), developed recently [34]. Symmetry-Adapted Perturbation Theory (SAPT) has two advantages over supermolecular methods. First, it requires only monomer properties, so there is no need to compute a dimer wave function. For MC wave functions, the latter may be problematic if size-consistency has to be preserved. The second appealing feature of SAPT is that the interaction energy is given as a sum of physically meaningful components which provide insight into the character of the interaction. SAPT(MC) can be applied with any ab initio model that gives access to 1- and 2-RDMs of monomers. The method predicts the interaction energy through second-order in the interaction operator

$$E^{\text{SAPT(MC)}} = E_{\text{elst}}^{(1)} + E_{\text{exch}}^{(1)} + E_{\text{ind}}^{(2)} + E_{\text{exch-ind}}^{(2)} + E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)} + E_{\text{exch-disp}}^{(2)}, \quad (12)$$

where the first-order terms, $E_{\text{elst}}^{(1)}$, $E_{\text{exch}}^{(1)}$, are electrostatic and exchange components, respectively, while the second-order components include induction, $E_{\text{ind}}^{(2)} + E_{\text{exch-ind}}^{(2)}$, and dispersion, $E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)} + E_{\text{exch-disp}}^{(2)}$, energy terms. Until recently, the most time consuming steps in SAPT(MC) have been the calculation of the second-order dispersion components. By using the algorithms presented in Eqs. (10) and (11), one of the bottlenecks has been removed—now the $E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)}$ term can be computed at a moderate cost. Similar approach as adopted for the $E_{\text{disp}}^{(2)}$ component could be developed for the exchange-dispersion energy, $E_{\text{exch-disp}}^{(2)}$. It would lower its computational cost by one order of magnitude. Work along this line is in progress.

Demonstrations

Molecular interaction between molecules in out-of-equilibrium geometries

Molecular interactions in complexes involving out-of-equilibrium-geometry molecules, i.e., molecules with stretched bonds, has remained a challenge for theoretical methods. The difficulty in describing such systems stems from two crucial electron correlation effects which must be accounted for in a balanced way: a short-range static correlation and a long-range dynamic correlation giving rise to the dispersion interaction. Recently, we have conducted a SAPT(MC) study on molecular interactions in strained linear chains to elucidate how the interactions change under strain [35]. As model systems, we have used the acetylene and diacetylene dimers. The efficient multireference wavefunction of choice has been the Generalized Valence Bond Perfect-Pairing (GVB-PP). We have shown that simultaneous elongation of all carbon-carbon covalent bonds in interacting linear chains leads initially to enhancement of molecular attraction. Upon further bond stretching, the inter-chain interaction decreases, ultimately turning from attractive to repulsive. SAPT(MC) analysis has revealed that observed changes result from the interplay between the increasing dispersion energy (attractive interaction) and exchange (repulsive) interaction. The latter energy component dominates for sufficiently stretched chains, resulting in an overall repulsive interaction. The pattern observed for a strained model of molecular chains—from more attractive to repulsive—is universal. Similar behaviour is expected to be observed in 1D and 2D nanomaterials.

Molecular interactions in van der Waals complexes with a single localised exciton

We have applied SAPT(MC) to study noncovalent interactions in low-lying excited-state complexes either of a $\pi - \pi^*$ or $n - \pi^*$ character [9, 33]. Such excitations are the keystone of organic photochemistry. Creation of a localized exciton affects the binding—these subtle energetic effects can now be studied in detail by the interaction energy decomposition.

It is a common belief that the redistribution of electron density resulting from the creation of an exciton leads to increased polarizability and, consequently, to an enhanced dispersion attraction. Our study shows that this is not always the case, since a weakened binding in the excited state may result from a marked decrease in both electrostatic and dispersion energy components. As examples, in Figures 17 and 18 we present changes of the interaction energy and its components in benzene $\pi - \pi^*$ and peptide $n - \pi^*$ complexes after the generation of a single exciton localised on the organic molecule (benzene or peptide). Although excited states are characterized by a reduced Pauli repulsion (exchange energy), this effect does not compensate for the change in electrostatic and dispersion attraction. In Figure 18, we show three complexes of peptide, in which it is the electrostatic attraction, not dispersion, that is the main binding interaction energy component. For such complexes, the appearance of an exciton is expected to have a small effect on the dispersion interaction and mostly affect the electrostatic energy, which becomes less binding. Indeed, as can be inferred from Figure 18, decreasing electrostatics is almost entirely responsible for the destabilisation of peptide complexes.

Thanks to developing a novel efficient algorithm for the dispersion energy and to the advancement in the GammCor code, it has been possible to extend the applicability of SAPT(MC) from small- to medium-sized complexes [33]. The SAPT(MC) analysis has shown that in low-lying excited states the dispersion energy may be the driving force behind the stability of the complex. Spatial mapping of the dispersion energy density has helped to identify the regions affected most by the exciton.

Code used

Calculations presented in the Demonstrations section have been carried out in the GammCor program, one of the flagship codes of TREX. GammCor is a quantum chemistry code for Multiconfigurational Symmetry Adapted Perturbation Theory, SAPT(MC). GammCor can be interfaced with any other quantum chemistry code which provides density matrices from wavefunction or wavefunction-free calculations. In due course of realizing the TREX project, GammCor has been substantially rewritten in order to achieve speed up in calculations and to extend the applicability of SAPT(MC) to larger molecular systems. Currently, the code is able to treat molecules comprising a few tens of atoms and basis sets exceeding 1000 one-electron functions. The latest version of GammCor is capable of handling more than 50 active electrons in more than 100 active orbitals. Progress in GammCor's computational abilities has been realized through: improved handling of two electron integrals, concerning both memory requirements and scaling of the computational cost with the increase of the system size, development and implementation of novel computational algorithms for the dispersion energy and SAPT(MC), improved vectorization and parallelization of the code, improved interoperability of GammCor with other quantum chemistry codes, such as Molpro, Dalton, ORCA, and by integrating the TREXIO I/O library to obtain atomic integrals and reduced density matrices from external software. More details can be found in the D2.6 deliverable.

Benzene...Water
 $\pi - \pi^*$

Benzene...MeOH
 $\pi - \pi^*$

Benzene...MeNH₂
 $\pi - \pi^*$

	$E_{es} - E_{gs}$		
	H ₂ O	MeOH	MeNH ₂
$\Delta E_{elst}^{(1)}$	0.88	0.98	0.54
$\Delta E_{exch}^{(1)}$	-0.35	-0.45	-0.25
$\Delta E_{ind}^{(2)}$	0.11	0.15	0.08
$\Delta E_{exch-ind}^{(2)}$	-0.05	-0.08	-0.03
$\Delta E_{disp}^{(2)}$	0.17	0.24	0.22
$\Delta E_{exch-disp}^{(2)}$	-0.05	-0.07	-0.05
ΔE_{int}^{SAPT}	0.72	0.77	0.50

- stabilization
+ destabil.
kcal/mol

Figure 17: Changes in SAPT(MC) interaction energy and its components for benzene complexes induced by the generation of the $\pi - \pi^*$ exciton.[9]

6 Conclusions

The activities carried out within WP5 have led to demonstrations in solid state systems with unprecedented system sizes, in studying strained 2D materials, in magnetic clusters with exponentially large spin degeneracy, in modelling relevant tough elusive intermolecular dispersive interactions for out-of-equilibrium and excited-state configurations. Newly implemented functionalities (WP1), accrued interoperability (WP2), codes modularization (WP3), high-throughput mode and integration with the generation of machine learning potentials (WP4) have been beneficial to reach these goals. Finally, challenging systems from the chemical and/or physical perspective became new benchmarks where the efficiency and scalability of different codes of the TREX family have been checked.

Peptide...Water
 $n - \pi^*$

Peptide...MeNH₂
 $n - \pi^*$

	$E_{es} - E_{gs}$	
	H ₂ O	MeNH ₂
$\Delta E_{elst}^{(1)}$	0.71	0.71
$\Delta E_{exch}^{(1)}$	-0.03	0.05
$\Delta E_{ind}^{(2)}$	0.12	-0.12
$\Delta E_{exch-ind}^{(2)}$	-0.03	0.32
$\Delta E_{disp}^{(2)}$	-0.01	-0.10
$\Delta E_{exch-disp}^{(2)}$	0.01	0.05
ΔE_{int}^{SAPT}	0.77	0.91

- stabilization
+ destabil.
kcal/mol

Figure 18: Changes in SAPT(MC) interaction energy and its components for peptide complexes induced by the generation of the $n - \pi^*$ exciton [9].

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